

Teaching Reading to Intermediate Phase Learners in Inclusive Farm Schools: Challenges and Suggested Strategies

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Abstract:- This article reports on a study that focused on the challenges experienced by teachers in teaching reading in inclusive farm schools in Klerksdorp district. The purpose of this study was to explore the strategies to improve the teaching of reading to learners in farm inclusive school in Dr, Kenneth Kaunda district. The other purpose is to inculcate the spirit and love of reading for comprehension in intermediate phase and to encourage the leadership on reading in inclusive farm schools.

The set objectives for the study was to explore challenges experienced by teachers in teaching reading and to explore the teaching strategies that will enhanced successful reading in inclusive school. A qualitative research approach was followed, underpinned by interpretive method as a paradigm. Participants were purposefully selected. Data were collected through semi-structured interviews. The participants included were from three inclusive farm schools.

Participants encapsulates one principal from each school as the managers and responsible for the implementation of teaching reading in inclusive schools. One subject advisor who is responsible for developing teachers in improving teaching of reading in farm schools. Two teachers from each of three schools who are the implementers of teaching reading of were also selected. Participants involved in this study were ten in number.

Keywords:- Inclusive classroom, inclusive farm school, intermediate phase, language of teaching and learning (LoLT), Teaching reading, Teaching English first additional language (EFAL).

I. INTRODUCTION

Reading is an important element of the curriculum in primary school. It is important that learners should in learners must be equipped with the necessary reading skills that will enable them to successfully challenge any comprehension question in their assessment. **Hence the study:** teaching reading to learners in intermediate phase inclusive farm schools.

Previous research by (Bruwer, Hartel & Steyn 2014) concurred that teachers are not adequately supported and trained in teaching reading in school. Teachers lack more skills and knowledge in the selection and implementation of teaching reading. Educator's inability to make use of proper teaching strategies in teaching reading have resulted in learner poor academic performance in their formal assessment, Bruwer, Hartel and Steyn (2014). The above challenge was aggravated by the lack of provision of resources to enhance the teaching of reading in farm schools. It is not every qualified teacher can teach reading especially in intermediate phase. It needs teacher with relevant skills who can apply differentiated teaching approaches in teaching reading.

The study revolves around the interpretive paradigm which intends to explore teachers experience in teaching farm schools learners reading. Educator's knowledge and experience were considered during the empirical study when interviews were conducted. The study took place in three farms schools which are vulnerable around Klerksdorp periphery were most of the parents are unemployed and the rate of learner drop out is very high. It has been a norm in our vulnerable farm schools that reading has not been our hobby, concurred (Kepe 2017) by stating that readership in South African schools has become major challenge for teacher of English first additional language.

Therefore it is imperative that teachers who are teaching learners reading be made in an entertaining manner that they enjoy reading thus will uplift their academic qualifications.

➤ *Challenges experienced in teaching reading in intermediate phase learners*

- The main challenge with teaching reading in farm schools is lack of teaching skill and approaches that will make learner read.
- Inadequate subject knowledge of teachers is among factors contributing to learners inability to read, (Richard & Ibrahim, 2014)
- Sources with font that are not of assistance to learners with reading challenges
- Teachers mostly focusing on completion of curriculum than making sure that reading skills are fully developed in intermediate phase learners.

- Teachers failing to apply for learner's concessions and accommodation on time thus compromise reading skill development in intermediate phase learners (SIAS policy: 2014).
- Lack of provision of reading materials has been a challenge in rural schools, and it postulates major problems in the learning of English language. UNESCO (2006) states that teaching reading requires a variety of materials is important for it enables a better understanding
- Lack of proper word pronunciation.

Several African countries also stipulated numerous challenges experienced by teachers in teaching reading in schools, inter alia Kenyan researcher Crouch *et al* divulged that

- Over crowding in the classroom
- Irrelevant teaching method in pre-schools
- Large number of absenteeism.

➤ *Teacher's knowledge and orientations to reading:*

Teacher's perception of reading and their own reading practices may also contribute to learners low literacy level. It was affirmed by researchers that poor preparation, lack of resources, poor reading facilities also aggravate the challenge in teaching reading in primary school learners (Du Plessis, Pierre, & Mestry, Raj: 2019). All the above stipulated challenges needs to be addressed in order to have learners mastering reading in intermediate phase.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

It has recently been a lamentation that learners in most South African schools cannot read and write. Reading comprehension is a complex task which depends on a range of cognitive and linguistic processes, (Rule & Land, 2017). Reading difficulties are the main causes of failure in school. Recent researchers attributed that between 10 per cent and 15 per cent of school-going learners have reading difficulties, (Kate, 2019). It is the responsibility of teachers to identify learners problems including those related to reading from a holistic point of view in order to help such a learner manage academically in school concurred (Kate, 2019). It is educators to screen learners with reading barriers at early stage so that they are able to provide them with appropriate early intervention strategies.

It is through reading that learners may acquire the subject content thus will enhance understanding of the delivery of the content. It relies solely on teachers knowledge on the content.

III. THEORETICAL FRAME WORK

This study adopted reading readiness theory and behaviorist theory. Both theories were selected because they were found to be augmenting one another in enhancing the

teaching of reading in schools. Both theorists observed in an analysis of children's reading errors, which he called miscues, he and his colleagues produced evidence that children almost instinctively try to make sense of what they are doing when they read. He uses miscues as a window on the reading process and characteristics, Nation (2019).

This process as, in a much-quoted phrase, a psycholinguistic guessing and phonic cueing systems, have a role, they are seen as a subordinate to prediction based upon cues from syntax and meaning (Agyei 2019). The behaviorists see language learning as habit formation. They insisted that error is inhibitory in language learning and so a speaker of a language should through stimulus and response practice learn language so perfectly that he makes no error in his language. The behaviorist suggested that learners should be subjected to drills, pattern practical, repetition and other useful techniques to enable them learn the second language perfectly (Kim, 2020). Reading is regarded as a process that moves from the parts to the whole (bottom up).

➤ *Research questions*

Research questions were outlined as follows:

- What are the challenges experienced by teachers in teaching reading to learners in intermediate phase in primary schools?
- How challenges experience by teachers in teaching reading in intermediate phase will be addressed?
- What reading strategies are used in the teaching of reading in intermediate phase learners?

➤ *Purpose of the study*

The purpose of the study is to explore challenges experienced by teachers in teaching reading in intermediate phase learners. The study would help teachers teaching reading to identify their challenges and bring about introduction of relevant teaching strategies and recommendations in order to improve teaching of reaching in their schools. The researcher intends to bring awareness to basic education management that learners needs to comprehend the subject contend through reading therefore reading must be prioritised to bring about positive results.

➤ *Population sampling selection of participant*

Purposive sampling was employed in this study to select participants. Participants were from two selected primary schools which are classified as farm schools. Two Senior Education Specialist (SES) who were responsible for promoting the teaching of reading in schools, were used. In addition, four teachers (two from each school) who were, at the time of research undergoing in service-training on how to teach reading to learners in intermediate phase. Four learners (two learners from each school) were also selected. These are learners who are struggling with reading. Lastly two principals were selected as they manage the teaching of reading in schools.

Table 1: Outlining the participant in three selected farm schools

	Teachers	Principals	Learners	Senior Education Specialists (SES)
School 1	2	1	2	1
School 2	2	1	2	1
Totals	4	2	4	2

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study adopted qualitative research approach, as it is intended to gain an understanding of the challenges from the teachers' point of view that they face whilst teaching reading in farm school learners. Qualitative research explains and reveals what occurs in true-to-life situations such as a school and a classroom (Denzin and Lincoln 2020).

V. DISCUSSIONS

The aim of this article was to understand the challenges experienced by teachers when teaching farm school learners who experience reading problems. Reading can improve learners vocabulary acquisition and knowledge on spelling and writing, (Alshahrani, 2019). The problem on teaching reading in farm schools deal with three basic conditions, each of which deals with reading instruction. The second problems pertain from the fact that reading takes place in the classroom and where there are no enough reading materials to read it is great challenge.

The last identified challenge is that teacher are offer not trained to teach reading, yes all teachers are qualified but not every teacher can teach reading especially in farm schools where learners are from magionalised families where most parents do not have love of reading.

VI. CONCLUSION

The teaching of reading in primary schools was found to be a challenging factor as most teachers are not well trained. Lack of educators training was aggravated by many factors, inter alia, lack of availability of reading materials, large number of learners in the classroom, poor reading background as a results of poor instruction in pre-schools and less use of english than home language.

In summary, the reading strategies, storybook reading strategies, memorizing strategies, writing strategies are effective for enhancing accumulation of vocabulary skills and speakers, and/or have learning disabilities. In order to address the insuing challenges and limitations, an immediate interaction must be put in place to transform the manner in which teachers are teaching reading in schools. Teachers training and continuous support is essential to promote reading schools. Developing better ways in which teachers approach teaching reading in schools may results in inculcating reading community.

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